

This is actually the reason why I started writing online. I wanted to do it for myself – to share my thoughts and get feedback on them. But oftentimes, writing has some sort of therapeutic effect on me. My mind is always full of ideas and thoughts, and writing them down really helps me in many situations.

Don't be afraid to share failure and things you regret but learned from. Life is not always sunny and there will always be people trying to drag others down. Even more so online, but don't let them discourage you because when you write, you write for yourself!

- **Publicity**

Another valid reason for writing online is to gain public attention – whether for yourself, your product, or your company. A lot of people certainly write in the hope of becoming famous. And platforms like Twitter, Instagram, etc. support this with their clap and like systems. These small rewards can really be addictive and also dangerous.

I think it's OK to write for the rush, but there are definitely better reasons for writing. I believe that if you start writing without looking at those likes too much, it will not only be less stressful to write, but it will pay off in the long term even more.

You also shouldn't try to copy others too much. It's fine to get inspiration, but in the end, you should find your own way of writing.

- **Money**

Your writing can generate a substantial amount of (side) income. I've managed to generate several thousand dollars each month writing on Medium about programming and tech:

But writing for money is an art in itself, in my opinion. It needs a special focus. The focus on making money. If you want to maximize your ROI, you need to align everything you write towards that goal. Things like reputation or education are just side effects – not the main purpose.

When writing for money, you need to make sure that your articles are constantly read by a lot of people. And I mean lots and lots of them. At least on Medium, you need high exposure of your articles but also interesting content because the time each person spends reading your articles is an important factor for the algorithm that determines your payouts. Medium publications are a great way to increase the reach of your articles, so you should try to get accepted as an author for at least one major publication!

Another option to get paid as a writer is applying for paid writer programs offered by

internet businesses. Those are going to pay you a fixed amount, often between \$100-\$500 for one article.

Focusing on money and ROI is not so important if you choose a paid writer program. Your focus should rather be on meeting the criteria of the program in question.

Final Thoughts

There are many good reasons to start writing online. Some require a special focus for you to be successful and almost all of them benefit from each other.

But the best advice I can give you is to just start writing. Just do it, for whatever reason. Not tomorrow but today!

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